

Information Needs of Rural People in Food Stuff Trade in Abijang Area of Nigeria

Most rural people in food stuff trade in Nigeria are at the forefront in the fight against poverty, famine and food insecurity yet their information needs remains unfulfilled. This study was designed to give an insight into the information needs of rural people in food stuff trade. The primary objective of the study was to investigate the information needs.